

Expanding Omani Microenterprises through a Local Online Marketplace

¹Halima Abdallah Humaid Al-Maqbaliya, ²Halima Mohammed Abdallah Al-Saadi, ³Maryam Ibrahim Aamir Al-Shezawi

^{1,2,3}University of Technology and Applied Science – Shinas, Oman

¹ 66s1949@shct.edu.om, ² 66j196@shct.edu.om, ³ 66s1963@shct.edu.om

Abstract:

Omani men and women have experimented with entrepreneurship and started side businesses from their homes, particularly during the pandemic. Unemployed Omanis, as well as students, have started small businesses or microenterprises in order to support themselves and/or earn a living. These small or microbusinesses allow these people to earn money while also showcasing their talents, such as baking or selling handmade goods, or retailing. The majority of these online micropreneurs sell their products on platforms like Instagram, WhatsApp, and Snapchat. However, these platforms have many limitations because they are not designed for e-commerce and are only effective at marketing their products. Given these constraints, the researchers propose a web-based system or an online marketplace through which Omani microentrepreneurs can broaden their reach and simplify customer order processes, and customers can easily browse for products and order online. This project is an online marketplace, which is a type of an e-commerce website, where business owners and customers can interact. This project aims to assist micro or small local business owners in Oman in expanding their product marketing online by opening a shop in the marketplace and making it easier to sell and process customer orders. This system's users are identified as customers, business owners, and administrators. Its goal is to make selling and buying easier, faster, and more flexible to work with and organize, resulting in increased sales and lower operating expenses for business owners. Customers can also shop and place orders at any time. By responding to clients' requests, it saves them time and effort. More importantly, this web platform aims to help Omanis with manufacturing or selling skills by providing a venue for them to sell their wares, thereby expanding the reach of their businesses.